

Implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland

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Executive Summary

This paper proposes the development of a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation national node for Ireland (EOSC Ireland). EOSC Ireland will be a digital platform that connects researchers and research infrastructures across Ireland to the European-wide EOSC Federation. It allows researchers to share and access data, tools, and applications, making national and international collaboration easier. By engaging with EOSC Ireland, researchers can find and contribute new datasets, share analysis, and provide analytical tool and code that others can use, helping to advance scientific discovery.

To achieve this, EOSC Ireland must establish essential functions such as resource catalogue and registry services, identity management, service monitoring and accounting, order management, helpdesk and service management, and application workflow management. It is crucial to onboard national HPC and data storage resources, institutional compute and storage services, research data repositories, and thematic research infrastructures to create a minimum viable product (MVP) that is useful to researchers. Furthermore, the EOSC Ireland node must be enrolled as part of the EOSC Federation, extending the scope of Open Research from Ireland to a global context. This requires ensuring the 'EOSC Node Host' responsible for running EOSC Ireland must be a legal entity with a sustainable funding model.

Key Recommendations:

- **Appoint a Coordinating Organisation:** Appoint an organisation to manage a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) as described.
- **Establish Working Groups (WGs):** Form Working Groups to facilitate collaboration, conduct studies, and provide support services essential for EOSC Ireland's development.
- **Set Out Project Charter and Terms of Reference (ToR):** Define the project charter and ToR for the WGs, ensuring their ability to deliver the project effectively.
- **Provide Financial Support:** Allocate funds for project staff, meeting facilities, and ancillary costs to enable WGs to conduct their work and perform trials or Proofs of Concept (PoC).
- **Recognise WG Results:** Acknowledge the results produced by the WGs as authoritative to ensure their findings and recommendations are integrated into the EOSC-Ireland project.

Following on from this position paper, the next steps involve reviewing and consolidating the outputs from the working groups (WGs), ultimately developing a detailed implementation plan for EOSC Ireland. This plan will require approval and funding to support the full implementation phase. Once approved, the implementation plan will be executed: engaging stakeholders, providing training, monitoring progress, and evaluating outcomes. It is essential to ensure that EOSC Ireland is integrated with broader national and European research initiatives to maximize its impact and alignment with international standards.

By following these recommendations and next steps, Ireland can successfully establish EOSC Ireland, enhancing its research infrastructure and contributing to the global Open Science movement.

Conversely, excessive delays in decision making and insufficient investment in EOSC Ireland, presents a significant risk to the Irish research ecosystem, both in terms of falling behind our research

partners in the provision of supports to researchers, and reputationally, diminishing our standing as a leader in Open Science.

Introduction

The purpose of this position paper is to propose the development of a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation national node for Ireland (EOSC Ireland). It aims to outline the strategic importance of EOSC Ireland in enhancing national and international research collaboration, improving access to research infrastructures, and aligning with European Open Science policies. The paper also identifies the necessary actions, requirements, and gaps to ensure the successful implementation and integration of EOSC Ireland within the broader European research landscape.

Open Science¹ is defined by UNESCO as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community².

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation is a collaborative initiative of the European Commission that connects national, regional, and institutional research infrastructures (RI) across Europe to create a seamless, open, and trusted environment for sharing and accessing research data and services. It operates as a federated system, integrating diverse repositories, high-performance computing resources, and research tools to support Open Science practices. By promoting interoperability, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles and cross-disciplinary collaboration, the EOSC Federation aims to accelerate scientific discovery, innovation, and reproducibility while aligning with European and global Open Science policies.

The **EOSC Federation** aims to provide Europe's researchers with the necessary digital resources to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders according to the principles of FAIR data and open science, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.

This will be done by putting in place a so-called 'system of systems' with an appropriate organisational and operational structure, between institutional, regional, national, and European data repositories, research infrastructures, e-infrastructure and other scientific service providers federated into a network of nodes — the EOSC Nodes.

An **EOSC Node** will be typically formed by multiple research institutes, universities and other stakeholders with a common geographical (European, regional or national) or thematic scope.

The expected outcomes of the EOSC Federation are as follows:

- Enhanced access to and use of digital resources
- Facilitated research reproducibility

¹ Open Science is often referred to as Open Research and Open Scholarship and these terms are used interchangeably in this paper.

² UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021) <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/>

- Increased collaboration, community and knowledge sharing
- Improved efficiency and higher impact of investment in research
- Increased standardisation and interoperability
- Better support for thematic initiatives
- Improved research integrity
- Increased robustness and trustworthiness
- Increased data sovereignty

EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

HEAnet is Ireland's National Education and Research Network (NREN). Nominated by Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS), HEAnet is the mandated EOSC organisation for Ireland. In April 2024, authored by their Research Engagement Team, HEAnet published their Vision to Implement the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland³, which included strategic actions for Ireland to develop its research landscape through participation in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Working with national stakeholders, including University College Dublin (UCD), Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI), Dublin City University (DCU), University of Limerick (UL), National Open Research Forum (NORF), Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin), Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC), Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI), Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Technological University of the Shannon (TUS) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU), this paper has evolved from a HEAnet vision to a national vision.

Since the publication of the original paper in April 2024, the European Commission has launched the EOSC EU Node⁴, the first node in the EOSC Federation, which serves as a gateway for researchers to access bulk data transfer, large file transfer, virtual machines, cloud container platform, interactive notebooks and file sync & share. This node serves as a model for future nodes.

Motivation

It is essential that Ireland invest and participate in the EOSC Federation, to strengthen the research outputs of Ireland, attract talent, and thus contribute to Ireland's economy and international standing. This will be achieved by providing researchers in Ireland with enhanced access to European research infrastructure, namely a federated network of research resources, datasets, and expertise across Europe. It will ensure that data and infrastructures provided by researchers in Ireland is accessible by researchers in other countries, thus expanding opportunities for citation and recognition, and so contributing to the impact of Irish research. It will ensure researchers in Ireland remain competitive, not least in accessing future EU funds which have been increasingly tied to the adoption of Open Science principles.

³ HEAnet's Vision to Implement the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in Ireland
<https://doi.org/10.23728/B2SHARE.A3412BCC801948CDA62D79552CE39B52>

⁴ EOSC EU Node <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

Participation in EOSC facilitates collaboration with other European countries and institutions and enhances data sharing and interoperability, supporting research and innovation for Ireland's research community. This will allow Ireland to play an active role in shaping the future of European research and innovation policies and therefore attract talent and investment to Ireland.

National Research and Open Science Strategies

Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy

Impact 2030⁵ outlines a strong vision for Ireland to become an international leader in Open Science and positions Open Science as a key policy agenda. This reflects the recently published Proposal for a Council Recommendation on the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2025-2027⁶ which identifies Open Science via the sharing and re-use of data, in particular through EOSC, as a structural long-term ERA policy.

Within the five pillars of Impact 2030, Open Science falls under Pillar Two: Impact of Research & Innovation Structures on Excellent and Outcomes. As part of good research practice, Open Research and a positive research culture will support the quality and impact of Irish research. It also falls under Pillar Five: All-Island, EU and Global Connectivity within broader objectives relating to the ten-year European Pact for Research & Innovation, the European Research Area Policy Agenda and national ambitions in Horizon Europe.

It is noteworthy that this national strategy emphasises the importance of Open Research in the context of improving infrastructures and interconnectivities.

Detailed here is how Ireland's participation in the EOSC Federation aligns closely with the strategic objectives outlined in Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy.

VALUE ADDED OF EOSC PARTICIPATION	ALIGNMENT WITH IMPACT 2030	RELEVANT PILLAR
STRENGTHENING RESEARCH OUTPUTS	Enhances research quality and impact by providing access to European research infrastructures.	Pillar 1: Maximising the Impact of Research and Innovation on Our Economy, Society and the Environment
ATTRACTING TALENT AND INVESTMENT	Positions Ireland as a hub for Open Science, attracting top-tier researchers and fostering a dynamic research environment.	Pillar 4: Talent at the Heart of the Research and Innovation Ecosystem
EXPANDING ACCESS TO	Provides researchers with	Pillar 2: Impact of Research

⁵ Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/27c78-impact-2030-irelands-new-research-and-innovation-strategy/>

⁶ Proposal for a Council Recommendation on the European Research Area Policy Agenda 2025-2027 <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/documents/proposal-council-recommendation-european-research-area-policy-agenda-2025-2027>

RESEARCH RESOURCES	seamless access to European datasets, computational tools, and expertise, promoting research excellence.	and Innovation Structures on Excellence and Outcomes
INCREASING RESEARCH VISIBILITY AND CITATIONS	Makes Irish research more accessible internationally, leading to greater citations and impact.	Pillar 1: Maximising the Impact of Research and Innovation on Our Economy, Society and the Environment
IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS FOR EU FUNDING	Aligns Irish research with Open Science principles, ensuring competitiveness in securing EU research funding.	Pillar 5: All-Island, EU and Global Connectivity
FACILITATING INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION	Strengthens ties with European institutions, supporting cross-border research collaboration.	Pillar 5: All-Island, EU and Global Connectivity
ENHANCING DATA SHARING AND INTEROPERABILITY	Promotes standardised data practices, enabling interdisciplinary research and seamless data exchange.	Pillar 2: Impact of Research and Innovation Structures on Excellence and Outcomes
INFLUENCING EUROPEAN RESEARCH POLICY	Allows Ireland to contribute to shaping EU research policies, ensuring national interests are represented.	Pillar 5: All-Island, EU and Global Connectivity

The National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030

The National commitment to Open Science is articulated in the goals and actions set forth in Ireland's National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030⁷. In turn, the National Action Plan for Open Research builds on several national policies and international recommendations including the National Principles on Open Access (2012), the European Commission Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information (2018), the National Framework on the Transition to an Open Science Research Environment (2018), and the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021).

The National Action Plan for Open Research aligns with the ambitions of the European Commission (EC) in relation to Open Science and strengthening connections to international infrastructures supporting Open Science and research data, in particular EOSC. Ireland's National Open Research Forum promotes active engagement with EOSC by supporting the contribution of Irish infrastructures and datasets to the EOSC platform, promoting EOSC resources, and supporting Irish researchers and institutions to use EOSC's system of federated data and services (NORF (2022), p. 21). By responding

⁷ NORF. (2022). National Action Plan for Open Research. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

to this recommendation, Ireland will ensure that its developments to support Open Science remain relevant at the international level and the continued competitiveness of Irish research.

Open Data Strategy 2023 – 2027

Building on the achievements of the previous Open Data Strategy (2017 – 2022), the *Open Data Strategy 2023–2027*⁸ outlines Ireland’s commitment to enhancing access to high-quality government data, fostering transparency, trust, and innovation.

The strategy aims to strengthen networks and improve communication between data publishers and users, to ensure the transparency, quality, and relevance of Open Data.

The three strategic pillars are:

- **Data Publishers:** Encouraging public bodies to release data that is high-quality, current, and adheres to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).
- **Open Data Platform Development:** Enhancing the national Open Data portal⁹ to serve as a central, user-friendly repository for datasets, facilitating easier access and use. With nearly 15,000 datasets from 160 publishers already available on the national Open Data portal, the strategy seeks to further develop and expand this repository.
- **Data Users:** Supporting individuals, businesses, and organisations in utilising Open Data to drive innovation, improve services, and contribute to economic growth.

The strategy is built on the core principles of strong data governance, open by design and default, and releasing data for innovation, and underscores the role of Open Data in enhancing public services, boosting productivity, and building public trust.

This aligns closely with the European Commission’s Open Data Directive¹⁰ and the Implementing Act on High Value Datasets¹¹, ensuring compliance, and fostering collaboration among public bodies.

The alignment between Ireland’s Open Data Strategy 2023–2027 and the European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC) lies in their shared goals around data openness, accessibility, and interoperability, particularly within the public and research sectors.

	OPEN DATA STRATEGY	EOOSC	STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT
SCOPE	Public Sector Data	Research & Scientific Data	Both contribute to a broader ecosystem of open and reusable data in Europe
PURPOSE	Increase transparency,	Facilitate open science,	Shared vision of open

⁸ Open Data Strategy 2023 – 2027. [Open.Data.Strategy_FINAL_ENG.pdf](#)

⁹ [Data.gov.ie](#)

¹⁰ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information. [Directive - 2019/1024 - EN - psi directive – EUR-Lex.](#)

¹¹ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/138 of 21 December 2022 laying down a list of specific high-value datasets and the arrangements for their publication and re-use. [Implementing regulation - 2023/138 - EN – EUR-Lex.](#)

	innovation, and public service efficiency	research collaboration, and data reuse	access to high-quality data
FAIR PRINCIPLES	Strongly emphasised (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)	Core foundation of EOSC	Harmonised data management standards
EU PRIORITIES	Implements the Open Data Directive and High-Value Datasets Act	Key initiative under the European Research Area and Digital Europe	Both support the creation of the European Data Space
INFRASTRUCTURE	National Open Data Portal (data.gov.ie)	Federated cloud-based infrastructure across Europe	Potential for technical and semantic interoperability

Vision

The EOSC Federation will consist of multiple ‘EOSC Nodes’ that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources within and across thematic and geographical research communities. The EOSC Nodes will be entry points for users to the EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own and possibly third-party services, including data repositories and services such as compute or software.

This paper proposes the development of a EOSC Federation national node for Ireland – EOSC Ireland.

EOSC Ireland is envisaged as a digital platform (software middleware) that connects research infrastructures across Ireland to the European-wide EOSC Federation, as well as to each other. It will enable Irish HEIs to efficiently facilitate access by staff and students to their research IT services as well as those provided by third parties across the EU. It will allow researchers to share and access data, tools, and applications, making national and international collaboration easier. By engaging with EOSC Ireland, researchers can find and contribute new datasets, share analysis, and provide analytical tool and code that others can use, helping to advance scientific discovery.

We emphasise that EOSC Ireland will focus on enabling a *single point* of access to services and resources provided by third parties, a so called ‘system of systems’.

Examples of these services and resources include access to national Tier-1 high-performance computing and data management infrastructures and services (e.g. those provided by Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC)), institutional and domain-specific infrastructure and services and resources such as those provided by Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA), ELIXIR Ireland, and other national, institutional or domain-specific repositories. It will be especially useful in linking diverse school/college level and multi-institution domain-specific resources to provide an EU-integrated/supported platform for efficient management of authentication and access (e.g. iCrag geoscience).

The figure below illustrates our vision of EOSC Ireland and its core functions, together with examples of services and resources provided by third-party organisations.

EOSC Ireland will enable cataloguing, discovery and use of digital resources such as:

- Data sets
- Data services
- Data Workflows and Open source Software
- High performance computing (HPC) and data processing services
- Storage services
- Virtual Research Environments (VRE)
- Applications

Services for handling sensitive data will also be accessible through EOSC Ireland. We envisage an infrastructure that enables federated data processing, where, as needed, algorithms and processing resources are 'brought to the data' - data visitation - to cater for cases where sensitive data is involved which cannot leave a jurisdiction, or simply because it would be impractical and costly to move large quantities of data.

As there will inevitably be access policies associated with the access to and use of resources and services available through EOSC Ireland, EOSC Ireland will provide monitoring and accounting services, including the ability for researchers to pay for the resources they use, either via credits-based systems or via digital wallets.

EOSC Ireland will ultimately connect to the Europe-wide EOSC Federation, thus extending the scope of its services from national to international. Researchers in Ireland will be able to combine resources available to them through EOSC Ireland with those from other countries through the Federation.

Further, EOSC Ireland will address current gaps in national infrastructure by establishing essential functions such as resource catalogue and registry services, identity management, and service monitoring. It will onboard national HPC and data storage resources, institutional compute and

storage services, and thematic research infrastructures, all combining to create a minimum viable product (MVP) useful to researchers.

EOSC Ireland will leverage synergies with national initiatives such as Impact 2030, the National Open Research Forum (NORF), IRL-DataSpace, and CASPIr, to enhance data sharing, interoperability, and support for complex research workflows. By integrating with these initiatives, EOSC Ireland will foster innovation, collaboration, and scientific discovery, ensuring Ireland's research community remains competitive and at the forefront of global research.

Given work already being conducted collaboratively between ICHEC and HEAnet, on the IRL-Dataspace (detailed further below), and its complementary nature to the development of EOSC Ireland, it is currently envisioned that HEAnet and ICHEC collaboratively lead the implementation and operation of the node in their capacities as national digital infrastructure providers.

QuarryLink: A federated edge-to-cloud data pathway for industrial-academic collaboration in EOSC

The QuarryLink Use Case offers a real-world demonstration of how federated research infrastructures can effectively bridge the gap between academic research, industrial needs, and public digital services. Originating from a live industrial site in County Cork, it will showcase how sensor-rich environments - such as quarries and ports - can produce high-value data streams, that, when governed responsibly, unlock meaningful insights for research, policy development, and innovation.

The use case will leverage key pillars of the EOSC Ireland node:

- **Federated Data Governance:** Through the application of site-specific governance protocols, registered and catalogued within the EOSC Ireland Node (e.g. iCAT) this Use Case will explore the practicalities of ensuring compliance, traceability and trust across diverse data providers and consumers within a federated environment.
- **FAIR Data at Source:** By enabling data to be discoverable and interoperable at the Edge of the site, the use case will investigate best practices for implementing FAIR principles across the Edge-Fog-Cloud continuum. The cross-cutting approach, spanning industry and academia, has the potential to offer valuable insights for shaping FAIR-aligned methodologies within the EOSC Ireland node.
- **In-Place Compute Efficiency:** Instead of transmitting large industrial or academic datasets across networks, this UC will explore how computational workflow can be brought closer to where the data resides – be that at the Edge, on Fog nodes, or within trusted HPC environments like ICHEC. Aligning with the principles of federated computing, the aim is to evaluate strategies where processing is selectively deployed near data sources or storage nodes, minimising data-movement, improving energy-efficiency, and enhancing data sovereignty. This approach supports EOSC goals for secure, efficient, sustainable, and scalable data handling.
- **Reusable Toolchains and Open Collaboration:** Through the development of containerised, FAIR-registered analysis tools, the use case will explore how discoverable workbench-containers will empower other researchers, institutions, and Small and Medium Enterprises

(SMEs) to reuse workflows, boosting the utility and impact of the EOSC Ireland infrastructure.

The goal of the use case will be to demonstrate a repeatable model for how a national EOSC Node can serve as a bridge between national research cloud infrastructure and the growing demand for trusted industrial–academic data collaboration.

The 4-Step Data Lifecycle

1. Edge-to-Fog Data Capture & Governance Initiation

At an industrial site in County Cork, a range of ground-based sensors generate continuous environmental and operational data. This data is transmitted from the Edge Layer to a local Fog Layer node, powered by a compact iRODS server. Here, the system performs sensor data aggregation, device-level orchestration, and enforces local data governance protocols. These protocols define how data is managed, classified, and shared within and beyond the site.

2. Federation with the National EOSC Node

The aggregated sensor data and the associated governance policies are both iCAT-registered and federated with the EOSC Ireland node. Data is then securely transferred to an EOSC-compliant Public Cloud storage facility in Cork City. Based on its classification, data is catalogued as either:

- Open and discoverable via FAIR metadata, or
- Restricted due to sensitivity, with access tightly controlled through federated identity and governance mechanisms.

3. Collaborative Open Toolchain Development via TUS

Researchers at the Technological University of the Shannon (TUS) in Limerick, connected to the EOSC Ireland node federation via their own iRODS server, collaborate with the industrial site to co-develop a containerised software workbench. This toolset is designed to analyse the Open Data portion of the industrial dataset. Like the data it operates on, the containerised workbench and its associated governance protocols are iCAT-registered, enabling FAIR discoverability and reuse by other researchers or industry partners within the EOSC Federation.

4. In-Place Federated HPC Compute via ICHEC

Using the EOSC Ireland node federation, TUS researchers request HPC resources from ICHEC, which is also a federated node participant. Crucially, the data remains securely in the EOSC Public Cloud - computation is brought to the data to ensure data residency, reduce transmission overhead, and maintain compliance with access policies

Once processing is complete, the results are returned to the TUS iRODS instance. Depending on the derived data's governance classification, it is either:

- Published as Open Data within the EOSC Ireland Node, or
- Shared privately with the industrial partner under the same federated access structure.

Broader National Context

This section explores the broader national research landscape directly relevant to EOSC Ireland. Open Science is a national and international policy agenda encompassing open access to research publications; research data and other outputs that are findable, accessible, interoperable and machine readable (FAIR); infrastructures for access to and preservation of research; skills and competencies; research assessment reform, and more.

The National Open Research Forum (NORF)

The National commitment to Open Research is articulated in the goals and actions set forth in Ireland’s *National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030*. The launch of the Action Plan in November 2022 inaugurated an ambitious national policy designed to meet three strategic objectives by 2030:

1. to establish a culture of Open Research,
2. to achieve 100% open access to research publications,
3. and to enable FAIR research data and other outputs.

Implementation of Ireland's *National Action Plan* is being overseen by the National Open Research Forum (NORF)¹². NORF was established in 2017 to drive the Irish agenda for Open Research.

NORF develops national objectives and coordinated actions to support Ireland's transition to Open Research, aligned with international objectives and coordinated actions to support Ireland's transition to Open Research, most recently through the National Action Plan for Open Research. Since 2022, NORF has administered the Open Research Fund, a competitive stream of funding, to deliver priority actions in the National Action Plan for Open Research and to foster uptake of Open Research in Ireland.

Services and Networks for the Web of FAIR Data

Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network

Sonraí¹³ aims to enable the development of data stewardship skills across the national research landscape through raising the profile data stewards, greater recognition of the need for data stewardship, professionalisation of the role of data steward and skills, and knowledge development throughout the emerging community. By developing these skills nationally, we can ensure the curation, preservation and dissemination of our national data assets, and the continued growth and development of our FAIR data landscape.

Open Repositories Ireland

Open Repositories Ireland (ORI)¹⁴ is a new membership organisation dedicated to advancing Open Research practices and repository services across Ireland. ORI promotes, supports, and develops open repositories and repository staff through networking, training, and advocacy.

Led by the University of Galway, the network brings together a consortium of fourteen institutional and organisational partners to enhance Ireland's open repository landscape.

Open Source Program Office (OSPO)

Open source software, shared workflows foster transparent, collaborative, and sustainable software development of FAIR data and software. Ireland hosts two leading Open Source Program Offices (OSPO), at LERO (University of Limerick) and at Trinity College Dublin, both members of CURIOSS the global Community of University and Research Institution OSPOs. OSPOs promote onboarding, interoperability, and resource sharing for federated, FAIR, and open science. LERO's OSPO is a partner in the EOSC-OSCARS mTess program, that will make over 500 RDM related training materials, best practices in cloud workflows (workflowhub.eu), and training materials on open source software, visible and discoverable in EOSC.

¹² NORF is a Government of Ireland initiative, funded by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS), through the Higher Education Authority (HEA). The activities of NORF are overseen by the National Open Research Coordinator. This position is based at the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI), which is headquartered under the Royal Irish Academy.

¹³ Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network <https://datastewards.ie/>

¹⁴ Open Repositories Ireland <https://www.universityofgalway.ie/openrepositories/>

Other relevant national initiatives:

- Responsible Use of Research Metrics (RURM) Training Module ¹⁵
- TROPIC (TRaining for OPen research in an Irish Context)
- National Open Access Monitor¹⁶
- iFrame Research Data Management Framework
- Incentivising Open Research Practices in Ireland (ABOARD¹⁷)

National Readiness for EOSC Ireland

The national landscape of infrastructures to support Open Science is complex and varied. In 2021, the members of the National Open Research Forum (NORF) published the *National Open Research Landscape Report*¹⁸ as a key step in the National Action Planning exercise. The Landscape Report identifies five defining areas of infrastructure that specifically support Open Research as follows:

- 1) Networking and computing infrastructures
 - Computing and storage infrastructure
 - Identity and access management
- 2) Meta-infrastructures, including persistent identifiers
- 3) Data infrastructures
 - Data processing and secure research environments
 - Institutional repositories
 - National research data repositories
 - Publication platforms and related services
 - Metadata aggregation and monitoring services
- 4) Thematic/disciplinary infrastructures
- 5) Quality criteria
 - Repository certification

Developments within EOSC since the publication of this report make plain the need for the day-to-day operational and technical co-ordination of the enabling infrastructures for Open Science, including Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), to facilitate their access by researchers.

National & Institutional Shared Services

Shared services play a crucial role, providing a centralized and efficient approach to managing and accessing research resources. These services facilitate collaboration among various research institutions, universities, and stakeholders, ensuring that resources such as data storage, high-performance computing, and research tools are readily available to all researchers.

¹⁵ RURM Training Module <https://norf.ie/responsibleuserresearchmetrics/>

¹⁶ National Open Access Monitor <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/>

¹⁷ ABOARD project <https://www.ucc.ie/en/aboard-project/>

¹⁸ NORF. (2021). National Open Research Landscape Report. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5q485c938>

By leveraging shared services, EOSC Ireland can reduce redundancy, optimize resource utilization, and enhance the overall efficiency of research infrastructure. This collaborative approach not only supports the principles of Open Science but also aligns with national initiatives like Impact 2030 and the National Open Research Forum (NORF), fostering a cohesive and integrated research ecosystem in Ireland.

IRLDAT: Shared Data Storage Service Pilot

Shared Storage service for active research data, IRLDAT developed and piloted a data storage solution that enabled the sharing of research data with collaborators from different institutions, within and outside Ireland, during the active phase of research. The project was based on the use of the B2Drop service from EUDAT diverse user groups engaged in the project, which delivered the definition of a national production service, along with costs and recommendations for sustainability. Funding for a production service has been requested and if successful, the service will become operational at a national level in 2025.

SURF Research Cloud

SURF's ResearchCloud is a cloud-based portal that gives Dutch researchers and their collaborators access to data, resources and services using a model similar to the EOSC-EU node. In fact, SURF plan to base their national EOSC node on ResearchCloud.

There is an opportunity, with support from SURF, to run a Proof of Concept (POC) trial on ResearchCloud, to understand how it can be used in Ireland to implement the basis of an EOSC node. This provides a secure, established and cost effective route to a POC for EOSC Ireland.

IRL-DataSpaces & IRL-DSSC (Common Data Spaces for Ireland)

Since October 2023, ICHEC and HEAnet have been working towards the creation of a Common Data Space for Ireland (IRL-DataSpace), which aims to address data-driven global challenges through collaborative Research and Innovation (R&I) between academia, industry and the public sector. The purpose of IRL-DataSpace is to cater to R&I-focused participation and usage of the data ecosystem by academic, public sector and industry participants for dealing with grand challenges and informing better public policymaking. This vision and activity is described in detail in the IRL-DataSpace Position Paper¹⁹.

IRL-DataSpace focuses on a structured, synergised unification of the national data ecosystem (composed of academic and public research bodies, and enterprise organisations where relevant) which is currently disparate and fragmented. IRL-DataSpace will be a federation of data stakeholders, data systems and services at a national level that also links with relevant European resources.

To catalyse this, HEAnet and ICHEC are also working towards establishing a national-level Data Space Support Centre for Ireland (IRL-DSSC) through which to engage stakeholders across the community for their participation and co-development. The IRL-DSSC will play a pivotal role in advancing the

¹⁹ Kannan, V., Wilson, N., Desplat, J.-C., Kenny, E., O'Neill, J., Sabatino, R., & Wearen, G. (2024). IRL-DataSpace & IRL-DSSC Position Paper A Common Data Space & Support Centre for Ireland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11350936>

current national data ecosystem into a federated, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), high-SLA and cost-effective ecosystem with robust digital platform resources, services for data sharing and governance, and a national level professional support team.

In this context, EOSC Ireland (as a national federation of digital resources focusing on the academic research community) will participate and interoperate with IRL-DataSpace to ensure seamless discoverability and sharing of resources between the two federations.

It is important to note that the scope of IRL-DataSpace is broader in federating data and resources across the academia, public sector and relevant industry for R&I, with particular focus on implementing security and governance for cross-sectoral and public sector participation for R&I-driven policymaking. Due to the complementarity between IRL-DataSpace and EOSC Ireland, it is currently envisioned that HEAnet and ICHEC collaboratively lead the implementation and operation of the two federations in their capacities as national digital infrastructure providers.

CASPIr National High Performance Computing & Data Platform

CASPIr (Compute, Analysis and Simulation Platform for Ireland) is the proposed national HPC and data platform and service. CASPIr will be composed of high-performance compute and large data storage infrastructure to underpin a diverse set of on-premises and federation services with both national and European stakeholders.

CASPIr will provide the digital backbone for R&I in Ireland, providing Tier-1 national HPC and data storage, and federate with Tier-2 (thematic and institutional) compute and data storage infrastructure, as well as European compute and data resources. For this, CASPIr includes access gateways to ensure performance efficiency with data governance and security, for linking diverse datasets towards solving complex problems.

In this context, CASPIr would be the national platform on which to sustainably develop and operate EOSC nodes as services, including EOSC Ireland.

National Persistent Identifier Strategy and Roadmap

At the end of 2024, NORF launched Ireland's National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy Interoperability, Openness, and Impact – Recommendations and Roadmap for an Irish National PID Strategy²⁰. This report sets out recommendations and a roadmap for a national persistent identifier (PID) strategy for Ireland. PIDs are a cornerstone of a modern, digital research system. They uniquely identify entities involved in research, such as grant awards, researchers, instruments, datasets, or publications, and enable structured information about those entities to be shared.

The vision of this roadmap is of a more efficient, transparent, and open research ecosystem in Ireland, one in which information flows more easily between systems and organisations, bureaucratic burdens are reduced, and research transparency and integrity are enhanced. PIDs underpin this vision because they act as bridges between systems, provide a rich information resource to reduce

²⁰ Interoperability, Openness, and Impact: Recommendations and Roadmap for an Irish National PID Strategy. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.sn00qt29n>

time-consuming and error-prone manual data entry, and can be used to automate processes and to demonstrate connections between entities, such as a grant and a dataset.

The importance of PIDs in EOSC is also recognised in the Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)²¹. It defines a set of expectations about what persistent identifiers will be used to support a functioning environment of FAIR research.

Thematic Research Infrastructures

ISSDA

The Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA)²² is Ireland's leading centre for quantitative data acquisition, preservation, and dissemination.

ISSDA is the national service provider to CESSDA, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives. As a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), CESSDA will contribute (meta)data and services related to Social Science research to EOSC, including (meta)data relating datasets available through ISSDA.

DARIAH-IE

DARIAH-IE²³ is the Irish node for pan-European Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities ERIC (DARIAH-EU)²⁴, it aims to enhance and support digitally enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities in Ireland. DARIAH-IE will contribute data, metadata and services related to the Digital Arts and Humanities in Ireland, to EOSC, via the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace (SSHOMP)²⁵, a domain-oriented discovery portal and aggregator.

iCRAG

iCRAG, hosted by UCD's School of Earth Sciences, is Ireland's Research Centre for applied geosciences. It leads integrated research on earth systems to support sustainable resource development and better human-environment interaction. Central to Irish geoscience, iCRAG connects public and commercial sectors through data spanning deep earth and deep time, advancing from traditional models to data-driven analytics via its Geodata Platform.

The Centre emphasizes accessible, citable geo-datasets, supported by infrastructures like metadata repositories, PostGIS databases, Docker-based storage, and EU cloud workflows in collaboration with ICHEC.

²¹ A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

²² Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA) www.ucd.ie/issda

²³ DARIAH-IE <https://dariah.ie/>

²⁴ Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities ERIC (DARIAH-EU) <https://www.dariah.eu/>

²⁵ Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

ELIXIR Ireland

ELIXIR is Europe's intergovernmental research infrastructure for health and life science data research, spanning 21 countries and 3 observers. ELIXIR maintains national databases, tools, compute resources, and training to advance open science and ensure life science data is FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—supporting innovative research in human health, agri-food, marine, pathogen, one-health, and biodiversity research. Ireland joined ELIXIR in 2016, but its growth has been limited by national investment. ELIXIR Nodes are often hosted by or partner with national HPC centers, for example, ELIXIR Finland is hosted at CSC – IT Center for Science. ELIXIR works closely with other EU life science programs including ECRIN, EATRIS, BBMRI, Euro-BioImaging, EUCAIM to coordinate major EU health and life science programs including the 1+ Million Genomes, Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) and EOSC-Life.

GDI-Ireland

In 2022, the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project was announced to facilitate creation of the data infrastructure needed to realise the European '1+ Million Genomes' (1+MG) Initiative²⁶. The overall aim of the ELIXIR coordinated GDI project is to provide a secure cross-border federated network of national genome collections across Europe. That is, each nation would have one or more data archives (e.g. ELIXIR EGA nodes), which provide meta data to a national GDI node so national genomic data is FAIR and available for research. Sensitive Human Genomics Data will not physically move across borders for analysis. 1+MG (to be delivered through GDI) is a federated system, whereby national nodes are connected by an overarching EU 'genomic data infrastructure'. Each national node will have to provide compute through a secure scalable secure processing environment (SPE) on its national data. GDI components include life science AAI, searchable meta-catalogue (DCAT), search engine (Beacon), data access security (REMS) and data streaming (htgets). Guidelines for SPE for GDI genomics data analysis are currently in development through EOSC-ENTRUST.

The GDI Ireland²⁷ (GDI-IE) project is the Irish arm of the wider European initiative. One of the outputs of GDI-IE is to create a long-term sustainability plan for the Irish infrastructure. This includes but is not limited to establishing a storage mechanism and secure processing environment (SPE) for human genomic data in Ireland. Genomics data will be part of the European Health Data Space (EHS) from 2031.

European Health Data Space (EHDS)

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) is an **EU statutory requirement** that establishes the legal and technical framework for accessing and sharing electronic health data across the EU, particularly for both primary (care) and secondary (research, innovation, policy) use which came into effect March 2025. EU countries including Ireland have established Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) to manage health data access. The availability of health data for research and innovation is a

²⁶ European '1+ Million Genomes' Initiative <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

²⁷ Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) Ireland <https://genomicdata.ie/>

requirement under the EHDS. It is anticipated that EOSC will provide federated cloud computing for health data research.

The HEA North South Research Program funded a strand II (€4 million) research program called the eHealth-Hub for Cancer which is developing requirements for all-island secondary use of clinical cancer data. It recently expanded an OHDSI-Ireland node with clinical, academia and industry partners who are performing real world evidence research. OHDSI (Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics, pronounced "Odyssey") is an open-science collaborative of 83 countries, developing large-scale analytics of observational health data research with health records of over 810 million individuals. Secure compute cloud infrastructure for sensitive health data will be required for OHDSI federated studies.

Summary of landscape

The Center for Open Science's strategy for culture and behaviour change²⁸ requires five levels of intervention represented by the pyramid below. These levels are progressive, reflecting the fact that successful implementation of higher levels depends on successful implementation of lower levels. Infrastructure is the base of the pyramid making behaviour change possible.

Center for Open Science Strategy for Culture Change

We see that the services and networks for the web of FAIR Data support communities, incentives and policy, for example Sonraí Irish Data Stewardship Network, Open Repositories Ireland (ORI), Open Source Program Office (OSPO), Responsible Use of Research Metrics (RURM) Training Module, TROPIC (TRaining for OPen research in an Irish Context), National Open Access Monitor, iFrame Research Data Management Framework and Incentivising Open Research Practices in Ireland

²⁸ Center for Open Science Strategy for Culture Change <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>

(ABOARD). At the infrastructural level we see both National & Institutional Shared Services and Thematic Research Infrastructures. EOSC Ireland seeks to provide cohesion between all these areas.

The picture below illustrates the landscape of initiatives and projects relevant to EOSC Ireland, especially in the Open Research broader context. The EOSC Ireland Core Functions, described below, are at the centre of the diagram, which together with national and institutional shared services and thematic research infrastructures will create an EOSC Ireland Node. These are complimented by the services and networks for enabling a web of FAIR Data.

Other EOSC national nodes

There are many examples of similar initiatives in other European countries, which are already production services and ready to contribute to the EOSC federation at European level. This is happening as part of the EOSC Federation's build-up phase. Thirteen Candidate EOSC Nodes have been invited to contribute to the first wave deployment of the EOSC Federation. Several commonalities can be identified among these Candidate Nodes²⁹:

- Many of the anticipated nodes are planning to contribute to the EOSC Federation via an incremental approach. They will begin with resources that are easier to federate in order to test as soon as possible a prototype of the Federation that can bring benefits to researchers in the short term.
- In most cases the Candidate Nodes are considering providing the Federation with a mix of general-purpose and domain-specific resources.

²⁹ The EOSC Federation's build-up phase is underway <https://eosc.eu/news/2025/04/the-eosc-federations-build-up-phase-is-underway/>

- Most of the Candidate Nodes already have a compatible Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure (AAI), as well as monitoring, helpdesk and accounting capabilities ready to be federated.
- Overall, the Candidate Nodes identified more than 60 possible use cases that could be considered for implementation. On day two it emerged that many of those use cases rely on data visitation, data transfer and sensitive data cross-node workflows implementations.

EOSC Finland

CSC - IT Center for Science³⁰ is contributing to the EOSC Federation by building up a national node for Finland. The node will be built in collaboration with the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture, the national Open Science Coordination and other national stakeholders that will be gradually engaged (and onboarded in the national node) via the EOSC Finnish Forum mechanism³¹.

The EOSC Finland Node will unlock access to national FAIR data, data services and research data management competence development. These resources will be accessible via a user-friendly entry point. The node will be accessible for Finnish researchers via the Haka federation, and it will be integrated with MyAccessID and EOSC AAI. The datasets, data services and training resources will be discoverable via the EOSC federated service catalogue. Through coordination with the LUMI AI Factory the national EOSC node will provide access to unique and large datasets and will also pilot a cross-node use cases on secure processing environments. As CSC is the main contractor of the EuroHPC Federation (EuroFP) tender, CSC will also promote interoperability between the EOSC Federation and the EuroFP.

Main Goals

- making Finnish FAIR datasets, services and research data management (RDM) trainings discoverable in the EOSC Federation (examples of national services are: fairdata.fi; research.fi; national data infrastructures and RI national nodes (e.g. FinCLARIN); etc.)
- making available unique, large size or restricted access datasets via interoperability with the LUMI AI factory
- making sensitive data discoverable and through authorisation accessible in a secure processing environment (for example in collaboration with EUDAT, ELIXIR, SURF)
- making the EOSC Finland node interoperable with EuroFP and the LUMI AI factory
- providing all the necessary core federating capabilities towards the EOSC Federation
- contributing to the interoperability framework and joint concept model development

Needs addressed

- need for FAIR supporting user-centric services that facilitate the research process
- need for RDM competence development
- availability of unique, large size and restricted datasets

³⁰ CSC – IT Center for Science <https://csc.fi/en/>

³¹ EOSC Forum Finland <https://avointiede.fi/en/networks/eosc/eosc-finnish-forum>

- integrating federating capabilities

Key Benefits

- demonstrating the value of a national node for the EOSC Federation as a whole and for the country
- increasing discovery and availability of FAIR data and FAIR supporting services
- testing interoperability between EuroFP and EOSC Federation
- bringing the EOSC Federation close to the private sector and their RDI collaboration with research performing organisations thanks to the connection with the LUMI AI factory

Who Benefits

- European researchers who can access Finnish datasets, services and RDM training resources on top of the other resources made available through the EOSC Federation
- European researchers and businesses that can access large size or restricted datasets
- European researchers who need to access and process sensitive data
- Finnish organisations willing to contribute to the EOSC Federation via a national node
- Stakeholders that will benefit from the integration of the EOSC Finland node in the LUMI AI factory ecosystem

Requirements for implementing EOSC Ireland

There are 3 phases of implementation of EOSC Ireland:

1. Developing and enabling core functions
2. Onboarding resources and services in order to have a minimum viable product (MVP) useful to researchers
3. Connecting EOSC Ireland to the EOSC Federation

Core Functions

Requirements

The Core Functions are described in detail in the EOSC Federation Handbook³² and comprise:

- Resource catalogue and registry services
- Identity management, providing single sign-on to the resources and services connected.
- Service monitoring and accounting
- Order management, where users can request services and pay for them where applicable

³² EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

- Helpdesk and service management
- Application workflow management, for example to enable researchers to deploy applications on compute resources, download data from connected repositories onto storage resources

These functions require the availability of an organisation providing the helpdesk and service management functions, and owning the implementation of all the other components, although third parties may provide the functions such as order management and workflow management and IT infrastructure to run the above functions.

In terms of skills required to perform the core functions, these are noted:

- System administration
- Platform engineering
- Data management
- Cybersecurity
- Legal/Data protection
- Governance

These core operational functions, combined with the other services and activities previously described, will ensure Ireland will have a fully functional infrastructure to enable Open Science in Ireland:

Gaps

Of the core functions, Ireland currently only avails of the Identity Management system, which is based on HEAnet's Edugate³³ federated single sign on (SSO) service. An Authentication and

³³ Edugate <https://www.heanet.ie/services/identity-access/edugate>

Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) compatible with the ARRC blueprint is currently not available. This would have to be implemented and would be based on GÉANT³⁴'s MyAccessID³⁵ Identity and Access Management Service.

While the other required functions are currently not available Research Cloud³⁶ software developed by SURF³⁷, suggested as the host for an Irish POC performs all additionally needed functions. Research Cloud is also being considered for use by Sunet³⁸ in Sweden and Switch³⁹ in Switzerland for the same purpose.

In line with Open Research practices the software used by the EOSC EU node is also Open Source, though compared to SURF's Research Cloud it is made of several separate packages with different user licenses, each needing to be downloaded and configured without any support.

Additionally, Ireland does not at present, have an organisation assigned to operating the core functions or allocated infrastructure on which to run the required core functions, making Research Cloud the preferred and most streamlined choice

Onboarding Resources and Services

Requirements

The core functionality described above is merely operational and will not serve as a minimum viable product (MVP) as no services / resources are connected, or 'onboarded'. To make it useful to researchers, relevant services need to be onboarded to the node, contributing to a resource catalogue.

As examples, and to develop a POC, relevant services could be a combination of any of the following:

- National HPC and data storage resources and services
- Institutional compute and storage services
- Research data repositories (thematic or institutional)
- Thematic Research Infrastructures (such as those described above)

³⁴ GÉANT is the collaboration of European National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) <https://geant.org/>

³⁵ MyAccessID Identity and Access Management Service <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>

³⁶ SURF Research Cloud <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/compute/surf-research-cloud>

³⁷ SURF is the National Research and Education Network (NREN) in the Netherlands <https://www.surf.nl/>

³⁸ Sunet is the National Research and Education Network (NREN) in Sweden <https://www.sunet.se/>

³⁹ Switch is the National Research and Education Network (NREN) in Switzerland <https://www.switch.ch/en>

Gaps

Several services are currently planned in Ireland which could be connected to an EOSC Ireland node, depending on readiness

The national high-performance computing (HPC) and data platform, CASPIr, is currently undergoing an upgrade with investment planned in 2025. Pending funding, IRLDAT will become available in 2025. Complementing these are several thematic and institutional Repositories and Research Infrastructures, for example GDI-Ireland, also planned for 2025.

However, onboarding these to the core service will require registry and AAI development, activities that will need to be explicitly defined and supported. Defining these requirements is one of the recommended actions of this document and will draw on the learnings from the build-up of the EOSC Federation.

Enrolling EOSC Ireland as part of the EOSC Federation

Requirements

Once operational, the EOSC Ireland node can be enrolled as part of the EOSC Federation thus extending the scope of EOSC Ireland from national to global.

To achieve this the organisation ('EOSC Node Host') running EOSC Ireland must be a legal entity with a Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) function and conduct Cybersecurity management according to established best practices and applicable standards.

The EOSC Ireland Registry of Resources must be pushed to the EOSC Federation registry so researchers from other countries can find and access resources from Ireland. Access must be managed, and resources must be monitored and the node continuously developed. For this there is a

requirement for sustainable funding for the infrastructure, its management, and the organisation responsible for it.

To facilitate the interaction of the Node with the Federation, each Node must nominate a number of persons in the following roles⁴⁰:

1. A **Coordinator** who represents the Node in the Federation.
2. An **Operation Manager** who is the contact person with the Operations Team of the Federation on operations.
3. A **Technical Coordinator** who is the contact person with the Technical Coordination Team of the Federation on technical issues (mainly IT issues).
4. A **Security Officer** who is the contact person for all security related issues.
5. A **Legal/Privacy Officer** for legal issues

Gaps

As outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook⁴¹, EOSC Nodes must be represented at Federation level by a legal organisation/entity. The chosen organisation may already be an existing legal entity, or a new entity may need to be established. While the chosen organisation would also need a Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) function, however this function is already well established within the Irish research landscape. The final requirement for connecting to the EOSC Federation is the ability to push the EOSC Ireland Registry of Resources to the EOSC Federation registry. While this functionality is currently missing, it is available through SURF's Research Cloud software.

A recommendation of this paper is to establish a working group to make recommendations on national governance.

	AVAILABLE	IN DEVELOPMENT	MISSING	OPPORTUNITY / SYNERGIES
CORE FUNCTION				
RESOURCE CATALOGUE			✓	
SSO	✓ (Edugate)			ResearchCloud, CASPIr, DARIAH-EU (SSHOMP), EOSC EU software
AAI			✓	MyAccessId from GÉANT, LS AAI in GDI
SERVICE			✓	ResearchCloud,

⁴⁰ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

⁴¹ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

MONITORING AND ACCOUNTING				CASPIr, EOSC EU
ORDER MANAGEMENT			✓	ResearchCloud, EOSC EU
APPLICATION WORKFLOW MANAGEMENT			✓	ResearchCloud, CASPIr, GDI, EOSC EU, workflowhub.eu, OSPOs,
HELPDESK RESPONSIBLE ORGANISATION			✓	Many organisations/ RIs run professional helpdesks, EOSC EU software, ELIXIR (Life Sciences), OSPOs.
MVP OPTIONS				
NATIONAL HPC AND DATA MANAGEMENT		✓ (e.g. CASPIr)		
NATIONAL STORAGE/ ENTERPRISE FILE SYNC&SHARE (EFSS)		✓ (e.g. IRLDAT)		
NATIONAL QUANTUM COMMUNICATION INFRASTRUCTURE (PILOT)		✓ (e.g. IrelandQCI)		
THEMATIC RIS		✓ (e.g. GDI-Ireland, iCRAG, DARIAH-IE)		All
REPOSITORIES	✓ (e.g. ISSDA, DRI)			All
INSTITUTIONAL HPC / STORAGE	✓ (e.g. RCSI, UCD-Sonic, DIAS)	✓		All
SUPPORT FOR CONNECTING RESOURCES TO EOSC IRELAND	UL GDI node and EOSC-mTess		✓	

Recommended actions

Considering the national vision for EOSC Ireland, the national context, including gaps in the current national infrastructure, and synergies with other national initiatives, a **Coordination and Support Action (CSA)** is recommended for the preparatory phase of the project to transition EOSC Ireland to full implementation in the next phase.

The actions identified are driven by the need to meet the vision set out in a timely manner so that the results are pertinent, to reduce costs by leveraging existing initiatives and skills, and to be inclusive of the stakeholders' needs.

There are clear risks to not engaging with the EOSC Federation and funding an EOSC Ireland node. These include:

- EOSC will be a key infrastructure in EU EHDS statutory requirement that health data is available for secondary data research.
- Not participating in the EOSC Federation will damage Ireland's reputation as a leader in Open Science and research innovation. This will affect Ireland's standing in the international research community and its ability to attract top-tier researchers and investments, which is a key objective of Impact 2030.
- The EOSC Federation aims to improve the efficiency and impact of research investments by promoting standardization and interoperability. Not engaging with EOSC will result in lower returns on research investments due to a lack of alignment with these principles.
- A significant amount of money has already been invested in Ireland's research infrastructure. Without a coordinated national node, research infrastructures in Ireland might continue to develop in a fragmented and redundant manner. This will lead to inefficiencies and higher costs, as institutions may duplicate efforts instead of leveraging shared resources and services.

Ireland will hold the EU Presidency from July to December 2026. Ireland's engagement with the EOSC Federation is crucial, especially during its EU Presidency. Active participation would demonstrate Ireland's commitment to advancing European research infrastructure and policies, enhancing its influence and leadership within the EU.

To ensure the success of the actions within the CSA (Preparatory Phase), it is essential that DFHERIS supports them by:

- **Appointing a Coordinating Organisation:** Designate an organisation to oversee the preparatory project leading to the implementation of EOSC-Ireland. This organisation will be responsible for coordinating activities, managing finances and budgets, and ensuring alignment with the CSA objectives.
- **Establishing Working Groups (WGs):** Initiate the formation of the Working Groups outlined below, potentially through the Coordinating Organisation. These groups will facilitate collaboration, conduct studies, and provide support services essential for the development of EOSC-Ireland.
- **Setting Out Project Charter and Terms of Reference (ToR):** Assist in defining the overall project charter and the Terms of Reference for the WGs. Formally approve these documents to support the project's activities and objectives effectively.

- **Providing Financial Support:** Allocate funds for project staff time, meeting facilities, and associated ancillary costs. This financial support will enable the WGs to conduct their work, perform trials, and execute Proofs of Concepts (PoC) of relevant technologies.
- **Recognising WG Results:** Acknowledge the results produced by the WGs as authoritative. This recognition will ensure that the findings and recommendations of the WGs are implemented and integrated into the EOSC-Ireland project.

Recommended Working Groups

WORKING GROUP		TARGET COMPLETION DATE
WG1	<p>Technical architecture, including analysis of synergies with other national initiatives to leverage them for a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for EOSC Ireland.</p> <p>Develop a technical roadmap for EOSC Ireland.</p>	December 2025
WG2	<p>Conduct technical trials/PoCs of relevant technologies, such as Research Cloud and any other deemed relevant.</p>	October 2025
WG3	<p>Determine the organisational structure for the day-to-day operations of EOSC Ireland and its governance in the longer term.</p> <p>Establish a sustainable funding model with associated required costings.</p> <p>Consider whether a new legal entity needs to be established.</p>	December 2025
WG4	<p>Technical planning for joining the EOSC Federation.</p>	April 2026
WG5	<p>Technical planning for adding services for handling sensitive data.</p>	December 2026

Once the WGs have completed their work, the organisation designated to transition from the preparatory phase to full implementation of EOSC Ireland will need to receive the necessary funding to execute the actions set out by the WGs.

It is anticipated that the full implementation phase would include review and consolidation of WG outputs, development of an implementation plan to be submitted for approval and funding. This would be followed by execution of implementation plan, stakeholder engagement and communication, training and capacity building, monitoring and evaluation, sustainability planning and integration with broader initiatives.

Continued Support for Open Research in Ireland

It is also recommended that support is maintained for the broader landscape of Open Research in Ireland by:

- Implementing the National Persistent Identifier Roadmap and Strategy: Support the execution of this roadmap and strategy.
- Funding NORF and the National Action Plan for Open Research 2022–2030: Continue financial support for these initiatives and consider longer term funding models
- Ensuring Sustainable Funding for Critical Research Infrastructures: Provide long-term funding for essential infrastructures, such as National High Performance Computing (HPC), essential EHDS secondary data use platforms including ELIXIR and services for handling sensitive research data.
- Defining Areas of Responsibility: Develop, agree upon, and communicate defined areas of responsibility and their interrelationships regarding sustainable research data infrastructure and its benefits to the national economy, involving DFHERIS, aegis bodies, funding agencies, and institutions.

Conclusion

The development of EOSC Ireland represents a significant step forward in aligning Ireland's research infrastructure with the broader European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation. By establishing a national node, Ireland can enhance its research outputs, attract top-tier talent, and contribute to the global research community. The proposed actions and working groups are designed to ensure a smooth transition from the preparatory phase to full implementation, leveraging existing initiatives and addressing current gaps in the national infrastructure.

The wider context of this initiative includes Ireland's commitment to Open Science as articulated in the National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030 and the strategic objectives outlined in Impact 2030: Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy. These frameworks emphasize the importance of open access, FAIR data principles, and international collaboration to enhance the quality and impact of Irish research.

The successful implementation of EOSC Ireland will require continuous support from DFHERIS, including financial backing, stakeholder engagement, and capacity building. By doing so, Ireland can ensure that its research community remains competitive, collaborative, and at the forefront of scientific discovery. Additionally, addressing the identified requirements and gaps, such as the need for a comprehensive identity management system and the integration of various research infrastructures, will be crucial for the project's success.

Glossary of terms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure. Edugate is an implementation of AAI, HEAnet's federated single sign-on (SSO) service.
CASPIr	Ireland's new Supercomputer hosted by ICHEC
CESSDA	CESSDA - the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - provides large-

	scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences.
Data Space	A distributed system defined by a governance framework, that enables trustworthy data transactions between participants while supporting trust and data sovereignty [https://dataspace-supportcentre.refined.site/space/Glossary/176554052/2.+Core+Concepts]
DRI	The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a certified trusted digital repository that provides long-term preservation and access to Ireland's humanities, cultural heritage, and social sciences data.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC EU Node	The EOSC EU Node is the first node in the EOSC Federation, launched in April 2024 by the European Commission.
EOSC Federation	The EOSC Federation aims to provide Europe's researchers with the necessary digital resources to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders according to the principles of FAIR data and open science, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.
EOSC Ireland	EOSC Ireland is a digital platform that connects research infrastructures across Ireland to the European-wide EOSC Federation.
EOSC Node	An EOSC Node will be typically formed by multiple research institutes, universities and other stakeholders with a common geographical (European, regional or national) or thematic scope.
EOSC OSCARS	OSCARS (Open Science Clusters Action for Research and Society) is a four-year Horizon Europe project that fosters Open Science with thematic areas Humanities and Social Sciences, Life Sciences, Environmental Sciences, Photon and Neutron Science, Astronomy, Nuclear and Particle Physics.
ERA	The European Research Area is the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU.
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ELIXIR	ELIXIR is an intergovernmental EU organization that brings together life science data infrastructure. Its platforms include databases, software tools, training materials, cloud storage, and compute. Established in 2013, it started its fourth 5-year cycle in 2024. https://elixir-europe.org/
FAIR	FAIR data are data which meet the FAIR data principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. These principles have been widely adopted by researchers, research performing organisations and research funding organisations, including the European Commission.
GDI	Genomic Data Infrastructure for the 1+ Million Genomes program, that supports federated sharing and analysis of EU genome data. Coordinated by ELIXIR
HEAnet	HEAnet is Ireland's National Research and Education Network, delivering high-speed internet connectivity and ICT shared services to all levels of the Irish education sector.

ICHEC	The Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC) at the University of Galway is Ireland's national centre for High-Performance Computing (HPC) providing e-infrastructure, services and expertise to academia, industry and the public sector supported by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Skills and the Higher Education Authority.
IRLDAT	IRLDAT is a project funded under the 2022 Open Research Fund to develop a national shared data storage service for active data, starting with a pilot for a small number of research groups with the aim to grow the service into a national service
IRL-DataSpace	A Common Data Space for Ireland to address data-driven global challenges through collaborative research and innovation between academia, industry, and the public sector.
IRL-DSSC	Data Space Support Centre for Ireland, engaging stakeholders across the community for participation and co-development.
ISSDA	The Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA) is Ireland's leading centre for quantitative data acquisition, preservation, and dissemination. Based at UCD Library, its mission is to ensure access to quantitative datasets in the social sciences, and to advance the promotion of international comparative studies of the Irish economy and Irish society.
National Open Access Monitor	A National Open Access Monitoring action of the NORF 2022 Open Research Fund to develop a monitor for open access at the national level, initially through pilot reports and a national dashboard to publish, analyse and track progress towards 100% open access, led by IReL.
NORF	The National Open Research Forum was established in 2017 to drive the Irish agenda for Open Research and is funded by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research and Innovation and Science through the Higher Education Authority (HEA).
PID	Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are long-lasting, globally unique identifiers for people (researchers), places (research organisations), and things (research outputs and grants).
RI	Research Infrastructure. In general, RI refers to equipment, services, human resources researchers avail of to conduct and support their research. In the context of EOSC, RI refers primarily to digital infrastructure and services complemented by human resources.
SURF Research Cloud	A cloud-based portal that gives Dutch researchers and their collaborators access to data, resources, and services, similar to the EOSC-EU node.

Contributors

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List of contributors

William Brown, Senior System Administrator (Research IT), RCSI

Chris Burbidge, Project Manager (Research IT), iCIRAG affiliate. UCD <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7457-1525>

Diarmuid Collins, Senior Systems Administrator, School of Computing, DCU

Aedín Culhane, Professor of Cancer Genomics, School of Medicine, Director Limerick Digital Cancer Research Centre, UL, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1395-9734>

Michelle Doran, National Open Research Coordinator, NORF, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7850-6886>

Lindsay Dowling, Open Research Support Unit Lead, Open Research Support Unit, TU Dublin
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7642-5326>

Venkatesh Kannan, Associate Director (Solutions R&D), ICHEC <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7201-6077>

Beth Knazook, Project Manager, Research Data, DRI <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3108-3921>

Ruth Moran, Graduate Education and Research Integrity Officer, ATU <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9235-519X>

Joan Murphy, National Manager, DARIAH-IE, Trinity Long Room Hub, TCD <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6428-5875>

Flaithri Neff, Academic, Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands MidWest
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1975-012X>

Jenny O'Neill, Research Engagement Officer, HEAnet, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1644-1236>

Roberto Sabatino, Research Engagement Officer, HEAnet <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-1468-342X>

Laura Whelan, Lecturer, School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences, RCSI

Shirley Wrynn, Research Integration Project Manager, ATU <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6944-621X>